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Research Article

**ROLE OF STATINS IN LOWERING UNSTABLE ANGINA
INCIDENCE AND IMPACT ON MULTIPLE TIME HOSPITAL
ADMISSION**

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the effect of lipid reduction on statin use on recurrent angina symptoms.

Study design: A case type and control study.

Location and duration: In the Cardiology Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018.

Methodology: In the first year of the study, patients who met the participation criteria were recorded. Data on presentation, gender, comorbidity (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking, BMI), initial lipid levels and symptomatic coronary artery disease were collected in a pre-filled form. Lipid reduction therapy was optimized in patients with altered lipid profile. In the second year of the study, data on angina symptoms and frequency of hospitalizations were collected and the relationship between serum lipid levels and recurrent hospital admissions was determined.

Results: A total of 1206 patients were included in the study, 594 normal lipid levels (group A) and 612 abnormal serum lipid profiles (group B). In the 1-year follow-up period, recurrent hospitalizations for symptomatic angina in 99 patients in group B were statistically significant compared to 36 in group A.

Conclusion: Patients with normal lipid levels require less admission for symptomatic angina than those who change their lipid levels.

Key words: unstable angina, Statins, serum lipid profile.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acute coronary syndrome (ACS) is the most common heart disease and includes ST elevation (STEMI), myocardial infarction, ST elevation (STEMI) and unstable angina myocardial infarction. Atherosclerosis is one of the most common causes of coronary heart disease. Dyslipidemias are increasingly recognized as an important factor contributing to the development of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases. The Framingham study showed that a 1% increase in total cholesterol resulted in a 2% increase in ACS incidence. Atherosclerosis is now recognized as an inflammatory disease, since it is the result of the inflammation and is based on inflammatory cytokines atherosclerotic plaques. Statins, 3-hydroxy-3-methyl glutaryl coenzyme A reductase inhibitors, are potent inhibitors of cholesterol biosynthesis and are largely cured of ischemic heart disease. Recent studies suggest that direct antithrombotic and anti-inflammatory effects associated with statin therapy may at least partially explain the reduction in cardiovascular events. The cardiovascular results are clearly seen due to an understanding of the biology of atherosclerotic disease, which may include vascular inflammation, endothelial dysfunction and plaque instability. The data from observational studies and randomized controlled trial was to emphasize the relationship between the early onset and recurrent coronary events and mortality reduction, supporting the routine use of Statins. Preclinical and clinical evidence also indicates that in addition to the lipid-lowering effects, statins improve inflammation, improve plaque stability and improve endothelial function.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This case type and control study was held in the Cardiology Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from July 2017 to July 2018. In the first year of the study, patients meeting the participation criteria were selected. Only patients

with unstable angina were included in the study. The data on presentation, sex, concomitant (diabetes mellitus, hypertension, smoking, BMI), lipid levels and reference drugs administered for symptomatic coronary artery disease were previously collected in a form of data. All patients with one or more of the main identifiable risk factors other than dyslipidemia, such as patients with heart failure, were excluded from the study. All patients began to receive atorvastatin after registration. Patients were broadly divided into two main groups at the beginning of the one-year follow-up period; Group A has normal basal serum lipid levels and group B has a altered lipid profile. Lipid levels were defined as a desired serum total cholesterol <200 mg / dl, LDL <130 mg / dl, and HDL cholesterol > 60 mg / DL13. In the second patient-group reduction therapy, lipid was also raised under the exclusion criteria, resulting in increased doses of lipids and statins to achieve the desired levels of patients to achieve targeted levels of monitoring. The patients who could not reach the goal formed the second study group. During the follow-up year, the frequency of admission and the rate of unwanted cardiovascular events in both patient populations were recorded. Data were analyzed using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) version 18. Chi-square test was used to determine the significance of the difference between the two groups.

RESULTS:

A total of 1436 patients were included in the study. During the follow-up year, 98 patients were excluded from the study, and in Group B, 116 patients targeted serum lipid levels and were therefore excluded from the study. Meanwhile, 16 patients in group B developed myocardial infarction and therefore could not meet diagnostic criteria for inclusion in the study. Of the remaining 1206 patients, 594 were Group A and 612 were Group B. The basic characteristics of the patients are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the patients

Parameter	Group A	Group B
Mean Age (years)	53 ± 7	52±8
Male	362	354
Female	232	258
Serum lipid levels		
Total cholesterol (mg/dl)	169 ± 14	234±17
LDL cholesterol (mg/dl)	78 ± 18	153±9
HDL cholesterol (mg/dl)	68 ± 8	30±4

During the follow-up period, 99 patients in Group B required recurrent hospital admissions. for symptoms. This difference was statistically significant when Angina group A was compared with 36 (Table 2).

Table 2: Frequency of hospital admissions for recurrent angina

	n=
Group A	
Single admission	558
Recurrent admissions	36
Group B	
Single admission	513
Recurrent admissions	99

P value: 0.001

DISCUSSION:

Statin therapy improves endothelial function and reduces vascular inflammation. In several studies, statin therapy confirmed ACS lowering and this was observed in patients with stable coronary artery disease, healthy patients, and patients with acute coronary syndrome. Other secondary protection trials have reported that hs-CRP-reduced levels with statin therapy are associated with regression to reduce the rate of atheroma load and cardiovascular events in myocardial infarction, revascularization and deaths. Plates lowering cholesterol can reduce the content of the coronary plaque lipid, which is less active and less prone to breakage. It is believed that this conversion of a less active or inactive active plate is responsible for reducing the cardiac events observed during drug treatment hypolipemiantes²². Our study revealed that an appropriate physician diet management significantly reduces the need for recurrent hospitalization of recurrent ischemic events that maintain serum lipid levels at both desired intervals, the frequency of recurrent ischemic events.

CONCLUSION:

In patients with normal lipid levels, there is a significantly fewer number of hospital admission for symptomatic angina than in those with abnormal lipid levels.

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